

Sayipova Dilafruz, in the name of Sharof Rashidov

Researcher of SamSU

"Boburnoma" depicts the mental state of a historical person

Annotation: This article analyzes the literary portrait, mental state, and personality of some historical figures widely depicted in Babur's work "Boburnoma".

Key words: Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, "Boburnoma", historical person, literary portrait, historicity, artistic interpretation, mental image.

After Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is a writer who became famous in the history of Uzbek classical literature by creating prose works, ghazals of dillrabo, qita, rubai, and masnavi. In particular, his work "Boburnoma" is translated into 32 languages of the world today, the treatise "Aruz" is a reflection on the rules of literary theory after Navoi's "Mezon ul-Avzan", the science of aruz and its intricacies, the author's thorough knowledge of poetic arts, his skill in choosing poems. , every stanza, the use of verse in place shows that he gave high importance to the poetic terms.

The simple narrative of the author of "Boburnoma" and the realistic expression of historical events, as the author noted, "For this history, the truth of every word must be known and the facts of every case must be edited ¹. " The assessment of all the historical figures mentioned in the work, facts, events, proofs prove that they are true.

Interest in "Boburnoma" began during Babur's lifetime, the work was translated into Persian, then English scholars Lane Poole, Monstewart Elphinstone, Edward Dawson, Mrs. Anetta Beveridge, her husband Henry Beveridge and others not only brought Babur's work to English readers, but also analyzed it. with the help of dictionaries, they tried to make the work readable and understandable to the students.

the complex political and social processes between the end of the 15th century and the 30s of the 16th century, the struggle for the throne between the heirs of Amir Temur continued violently, and sometimes one or another Timurizade took the throne at the top of the kingdom, as a result of which the armies belonging to one sultan are now the crown prince of another. joining the ranks and entering the struggle made the management of the kingdom in the political arena much more complicated. As a historical, autobiographical, scientific work, "Boburnoma" describes this complex process through historical events, the struggle for power, the frequent changes in the mental state of rulers, begs, and visionaries, the history of ownership and distribution of property, its consequences, and deep conspiracies. and we witness it described in a comprehensive, analytical manner.

If we look at "Boburnoma" only as a historical, adventurous work, we limit the skill of the author. It is literally a spiritual and psychological source. It depicts the history of Movarounnahr, Khurasan and India, the lifestyle of the crown princes of the three regions and the nobles around them, the lifestyle of their women, ordinary soldiers, poets and artisans, and the mental state of people related to the spiritual life of the time are described in connection with the most complex processes. Foreign and Uzbek scholars have also emphasized this feature of the work. For example, English historian Lane Poole, who was seriously engaged in Babur's work, writes about it: "His memoirs are not a simple diary of a soldier's military campaigns and retreats; In these memoirs,

¹Boburnama. Prepared for publication by S. Hasanov. Tashkent. East. 2002. p. 21. In the following examples taken from this source, the page of the source is shown.

personal impressions and subtle thoughts about the world are given by the owner of an impressive heart who knows Eastern literature very well, is a sensitive and knowledgeable observer, who carefully studies people, who can think about them objectively and justly². " Or let's look at the opinion of the English orientalist Monstuart Elphinstone: "In these memoirs, the life of the great Turkish king is described in detail, his personal feelings are free from any exaggeration and veiling. His style is simple and manly, as well as lively and imaginative. He describes the faces, traditions, aspirations, actions of his contemporaries as clearly as a mirror... But the bright character of the author gives the work the most charm»³.

If we draw a conclusion based on the opinions of the scientists mentioned above, based on the variety of artistic images in "Boburnoma", the description of the person's character and mental state in the depiction of historical figures, it is necessary to consider the victory and defeat, which is a typical situation in the life of the people of the time, in the context of the spiritual and psychological process. After all, historical events in "Boburnoma" were able to show themselves clearly in this aspect. In no other period have historical events changed so rapidly as in the end of the 15th century and the 30s of the 16th century. While describing the events of the same period in "Boburnoma", typological processes in the position and character of contemporary people are revealed before our eyes. This process alternates with the reality of time and space, bravery and cowardice on the battlefield, bravery and treachery, the joy of victory and the pain of defeat, especially in the depiction of winners and losers. Determining complex situations in the psyche of a historical person, observing and explaining changes in it is evidence of Babur's high skill. In the work, the changes in the mentality of not only the ruler, but also the common man, sometimes the triumphant celebration of victory or the bitter pain of defeat, or even the change in the fate of a person, is an extraordinary situation, which is described by Babur with a unique skill. Approaching this issue in this way, we intend to analyze, first of all, the situation of the tragic period for our society and history, people, their spiritual experiences through the materials of "Boburnoma".

The rapid exchange of events, the strength of dynamism, the sudden change of the mental and psychological process, and the impact on the psyche of individuals are skillfully described by the author of the work. Babur, the winner on the battlefield, soon becomes a loser, and again due to conflicts, he triumphs and becomes the winner. This change occurs several times almost from the beginning to the end of the work.

Victory and defeat occur in the mental state of Shaibani Khan, Husayn Boygaro, Khisravshah, Baqi Chaganiyoni, Kasimbek, Shahbegim, Ibrahim Lo'di and others, as well as the author of the work. In the artistic perception of victory and defeat situations, we come across such images as the high psychology of the writer, the spiritual change that occurs suddenly in the natural character and character, the signs of life beginning to fade and, on the contrary, the rebirth, which are important because of the artistic interpretation by the author.

Victory and defeat in the form of historical figures in "Boburnoma", the change of mental state that occurs in them, is such a wide and revealing aspect of literary skill that this situation requires in-depth analysis and comprehensive research in Boburology. After all, the scientific research of the mental state of the people of the time allows to determine the changes in the character of the person and the aspects that happened in it.

²Lane Poole. Babur. Oxford. 1899. S. 9.

³Singh N.K. Banerjee A.U. History India. M., 1954. S. 214.

In the framework of this article, we decided to consider the mental state of the winner and the loser in the person of Babur with the help of some examples.

of 1494-95 . Of the young prince Babur father for the first time Umarshaikh taking the city of Samarkand, where Mirza ruled, from the hands of Boysungur Mirza take to the throne at the time of possession . Young Babur's joy is endless . His grandfather is Amir Temur made the capital and great to the kingdom founded the famous city of Samarkand on the throne sitting d i. From victory shout drunk the prince in " Baburnoma". so writes : " Kill the throne of Samarkand, follow the begs of Samarkand like arrows and grace I got it . Let the begs who are with us be happy education and I had mercy . "4

At first glance, this text does not seem to show the artistic image of the victorious Babur's state of mind. In fact, based on the course of events in "Boburnoma" and the author's style of description, it is not difficult to notice the characteristics of the victorious Babur from the above passage. In the text above, phrases such as "I killed the throne of Samarkand, I obeyed and favored the begs of Samarkand as much as I could," "I trained and showed compassion" also indicate the mental state of the victorious prince.

In Babur Such a winning streak will last for a long time ca n't The long siege of the city , Babur around individuals , especially the betrayal of Beki Uzun Hasan because of this, Samarkand is out of control. Impossible Babur be k lar , lashkars I'm starting to leave . Just yesterday, Babur, the winner , suddenly becomes a defeated prince , and he himself writes about it like this : " Cherik of the world prey finished _ When Samarkand was captured, Samarkand was ruined I got it , help and egg and there was a need for piety . Chi place ulkim , the person is Andin what go ahead" 5. All together three months later, Babur , the winner , was overcome with depression and defeat . This too leaving Samarkand as he did not Road to Andijan received Babur again one conspiracy waits _ This Uncle Ali Dost " Babur is seriously ill " - that Andijan opponents with agreed _ Visit Andijan Castle the door Babur and for his loved ones closes _ Babur this is it describes the severity of his mental state at the moment as follows : " Andijong'a , Samarkand we gave Andijan was also out of the marrow . We are told that "heedless is less happy. " ronda and a little more in the world " - as if it happened Bisyar shaqq and shower came _ Why did he become a king? I'm sorry , that's it variety navcardin and province is not separated I melted , even myself knowing I'm sorry , it's a pain in the ass and does not know hardship I melted . "6

Babur expresses this state of mind very clearly , vividly in every way . In it sorry and nadomat , feeling sorry for one's worth and to traitors hatred , complaining about fate and to help did not come , on the contrary to the opposition side the eyes of admiration for the relatives who clicked looked at the question answer the defeated young prince who did not find - Babur's There is a state of depression .

A short time later later , in Babur's battles quite a bit mature , experience and conquer Samarkand for the second time ... It is impossible to lose it again in a situation he turns to Andijon . This text in "Boburnoma" now expresses the high state of mind of the victorious Babur, the victorious cry of the defeated Babur, who was in a whirlwind of hardships, which is important: "My father region, I have been growing closer for two years, but it has come out." By God's grace, he became a good man again in the month of Zulqada in 904. Sultan Ahmed Tanbalkim, Jahangir

⁴Boburnama. Prepared for publication by S. Hasanov. Tashkent. East. 2002. 62 p.

⁵That's it source , p. 62

⁶Baburnama, p. 64.

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Mirza and Jahangir were marching towards Osh. When they entered Osh, they beat Osh with a red foot and a black foot ⁷.

this text Babur – the winner, the victory over Babur's conquest, his Nashida directed by Ahmad Tanbal the defeat of the armies in an artistic, bright way sang – The phrase "Red-legged, black-legged". That's it in the sense of all its inhabitants. If it comes, the phrase "hit the target, hit the target, hit the target" says that this image the author by with great skill that it is described shows.

In general in other words, in "Baburnoma" only the author is the winner and defeated mental state alternating without standing, this process almost all of its characters is a typical event for Babur period and the price of time, its surrounded – studying the mental state of individuals not without benefits. This while Babur views that through period in people happened it also allows us to know the psychological process that will take place.

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⁷Baburnama, p. 69.